

Emotional Intelligence and Readiness in Teaching Practices as Predictors of Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention, and Understanding

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15568536>

Published Date: 01-June-2025

Abstract: This study is aimed at investigating the significant relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence, readiness in teaching practices, and effectiveness on handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding in the selected 7 public elementary schools in the Department of Education, Division of Davao City. It employed quantitative predictive research design which describes the relationship between two or more variables. Primary data was obtained by using adapted survey questionnaires among 200 teachers. Standardized Emotional Intelligence Test and teacher readiness survey questionnaires were utilized in this study. This study utilized Mean, Standard Deviation, correlation analysis through Pearson product-moment correlation, and multiple regression analysis. Results revealed a very high level and there is strong positive correlation among the variables. In addition, emotional intelligence does not significantly influence teachers' effectiveness while readiness in teaching practices have positive influence on teachers' effectiveness in handling learners with learning disabilities. This further implies that while emotional intelligence may be beneficial, it is the practical readiness in teaching practices that play more a crucial role in addressing the learning needs of learners. Hence, this research recommends targeted interventions in teacher preparation programs in order to foster emotional intelligence and teaching readiness and, eventually, create a more welcoming and productive learning environment.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, teachers' readiness, teaching practices, effectiveness, learning difficulties, inclusive education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Learners with Intellectual Disabilities (ID) face significant challenges in intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior, often characterized by difficulties in communication, social interaction, and daily living skills (Boat et al., 2015; Sulkes, 2024). While some learners undergo formal IQ assessments, many remain undiagnosed yet exhibit persistent difficulties in remembering, concentrating, paying attention, and understanding. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) acknowledges these learners through DepEd Order No. 23, Series of 2022, emphasizing the need for specialized educational interventions tailored to their unique needs. Effective teaching strategies, including individualized education plans (IEPs), differentiated instruction, and structured routines, have been shown to improve learning outcomes for these students (Sulkes, 2024; MentalHealth.com, 2024). However, a critical challenge remains—many educators report feeling unprepared to meet the needs of these learners, highlighting the urgent need for professional development and teacher training.

Emotional Intelligence (EI) and teaching readiness play crucial roles in fostering effective educational practices. EI encompasses self-awareness, self-regulation, social awareness, and relationship management, enabling teachers to create

inclusive and supportive learning environments (Banks & Banks, 2024). Teachers with high EI demonstrate better classroom management, improved student engagement, and enhanced integration of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) strategies, which foster empathy, self-management, and conflict resolution in students (7 Tips for Teaching Emotional Intelligence in the Classroom, 2024). Similarly, teaching readiness ensures that educators can adapt to diverse learning needs, implement inclusive teaching strategies, and build strong teacher-student relationships (Banks & Banks, 2024). These factors directly impact teachers' ability to support students with cognitive difficulties.

Globally, studies in the U.S., Australia, Finland, and the U.K. have explored the role of EI in teacher efficacy, particularly in inclusive education settings. Research suggests that teachers with higher EI are better equipped to manage the emotional demands of diverse classrooms and successfully integrate students with special needs (Collie, 2021). Despite the availability of professional development programs, many teachers—especially in low-income countries like the Philippines—continue to struggle with limited training, heavy workloads, and insufficient support systems, making it difficult to prioritize inclusive teaching (David et al., 2019).

Studies from India, South Africa, and Brazil highlight a persistent gap between inclusive education policies and actual classroom practices. While governments advocate for inclusion, teachers often lack the training, resources, and emotional resilience needed to effectively support learners with Intellectual Disabilities or Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention, and Understanding. Challenges include curriculum adaptation, classroom behavior management, and differentiated instruction, all of which require strong emotional intelligence and pedagogical readiness.

In addition, teacher mental health and well-being significantly impact instructional quality. Cowan (2016) emphasizes that teacher mental wellness directly influences student learning and development, reinforcing the need for school-based mental health programs. However, high levels of stress and burnout, often due to test-based accountability measures, continue to affect teachers' ability to perform effectively (Von der Embse et al., 2019). Research suggests that mindfulness, behavioral, and cognitive-behavioral interventions are among the most effective strategies for reducing teacher stress and improving classroom effectiveness.

Research from Malaysia and Turkey has examined how EI mediates the relationship between teacher stress and classroom management efficacy. Teachers who lack emotional intelligence often struggle to connect with students, leading to lower engagement and poorer learning outcomes for learners with Intellectual Disabilities or cognitive challenges (Bradberry, 2021). This highlights the need for teacher training programs to integrate EI development to enhance teacher preparedness and resilience in inclusive education.

In the Philippine context, Dela Cruz (2022) underscores the importance of EI in teacher preparedness, particularly in addressing the needs of learners with Intellectual Disabilities or cognitive difficulties. Filipino teachers with higher emotional intelligence demonstrate greater adaptability and empathy, fostering more inclusive and effective learning environments. Additionally, time management practices can further enhance teachers' productivity, allowing them to better support students with special needs.

The part of emotional intelligence (EI) and teaching readiness in helping students with Intellectual Disabilities or cognitive challenges is under-researched. As an independent variable, emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability of teachers to grasp, control, and react to emotions, therefore enabling inclusive learning environments (Lorenz-Walraven, 2016). Another independent variable, readiness, has to do with teachers' willingness to apply successful instructional techniques, which reflects their effectiveness in managing special education requirements ("Readiness and Efficacy of Teachers in Handling Learners with Special Educational Needs," 2023).

The dependent variable, teaching effectiveness, is measured by teachers' ability to:

- Implement inclusive instructional methods,
- Manage classroom behavior, and
- Improve learning outcomes for learners with Intellectual Disabilities or cognitive difficulties (Cagape, 2023).

However, inadequate support, limited training, and systemic barriers hinder the development of emotionally intelligent and well-prepared educators (Pestañas et al., 2024). Addressing these challenges can help develop strategies that leverage EI and readiness to improve teaching effectiveness and educational outcomes for learners with special needs.

This study explores on how emotional intelligence, readiness in teaching practices, influence the effectiveness of teachers in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding. This study offers significant benefits to various stakeholders in education:

1. **Teachers:** The findings provide valuable insights into how emotional intelligence and readiness can enhance instructional strategies, classroom management, and student outcomes. Consequently, this fosters a more inclusive and supportive environment for learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding.
2. **Special Education Administrators:** The results can be leveraged to improve teacher training and professional development programs. By doing so, educators will be better equipped to address the challenges of working with students with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding ultimately enhancing teaching quality and creating more positive school environments.
3. **Learners with Intellectual Disabilities:** Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding benefit from teachers who demonstrate higher emotional intelligence and readiness. They receive more individualized attention, achieve better academic outcomes, develop stronger social skills, and thrive in safe and supportive classroom settings.
4. **Parents and Caregivers:** Understanding how teachers' emotional intelligence and preparedness affect their children's education empowers parents to advocate for better support systems and promotes stronger collaboration between home and school.
5. **Future Researchers:** This study provides a foundation for further exploration of targeted strategies or interventions to enhance emotional intelligence and readiness in teaching, contributing to the continuous improvement of educational practices and policies for learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding.

This study aimed to determine the relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence, readiness in teaching practices, and effectiveness in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding. Specifically, it pursued the following objectives.

1. To determine the level of teachers' emotional intelligence, readiness and their effectiveness in terms of implementing inclusive instructional methods, managing classroom behavior, and improve learning outcomes for learners with learning disabilities.
2. To determine the relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence, readiness and their effectiveness in managing classroom behavior of learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding.
3. To determine the degree of influence of emotional intelligence, readiness in their teaching practices toward their effectiveness in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding.

The hypothesis will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H1: Teachers with higher levels of emotional intelligence are more effective in implementing inclusive teaching practices and managing the classroom environment for learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding.

H2: There is a positive correlation between teachers' emotional intelligence, readiness in teaching practices, and effectiveness in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding.

H3: There is a significant influence of emotional intelligence, readiness in teaching practices toward teachers' effectiveness in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding.

Emotional intelligence (EI) has emerged as a vital aspect of personal and professional success, attracting considerable attention in the realm of higher education (Shafait & Huang, 2022). The nurturing of emotional intelligence in college and university settings has become a critical objective, with educators and institutions recognizing its profound impact on students' academic performance, interpersonal relationships, and well-being. This literature review explores the multifaceted landscape of emotional intelligence in higher education, shedding light on key facets and influential factors that shape the emotional intelligence development of students.

Frameworks like Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and innovative teaching methods, have proven effective in fostering inclusive education for learners with intellectual disabilities or difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding. UDL provides a flexible framework that accommodates diverse learning styles, promoting accessibility and enhancing engagement (Yang & Ma, 2022;). Research highlights its success in improving interaction and knowledge acquisition in both self-contained and general education settings (Rao et al., 2017).

This study is primarily anchored on Goleman's Emotional Intelligence Theory (1995), which outlines five essential elements of emotional intelligence—self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills—is the main foundation of this study. These components are crucial for teachers to control classroom behavior and meet the requirements of students who have trouble understanding, remembering, focusing, and paying attention. The importance of emotional competence in fostering a positive and productive learning environment is highlighted by Goleman's framework.

Supporting this primary theory are Mayer and Salovey's (1997) Ability Model of Emotional Intelligence and Bandura's (1997) Theory of Self-Efficacy. According to Mayer and Salovey, emotional intelligence is the capacity to recognize, utilize, comprehend, and control emotions. It improves interpersonal connections and gives educators more coping mechanisms to meet the requirements of a wide range of students.

Furthermore, Bandura's theory emphasizes how self-efficacy—the conviction that one can succeed—influences drive, perseverance, and output. A strong feeling of self-efficacy enables teachers to respond confidently to children who struggle with learning and to apply successful tactics in the classroom. When combined, these ideas offer a thorough framework for investigating how teaching preparedness and emotional intelligence contribute to the efficacy of education. Since the emotional, cognitive, and motivational aspects of teacher effectiveness are at the heart of this study's focus on enhancing educational results for students with attention and comprehension issues, these theories work well together.

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study consisting of independent variables and dependent variables. The independent variable was emotional intelligence and readiness in teaching practices and the dependent variable is effectiveness in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding.

The relationship between emotional intelligence, readiness in teaching practices and effectiveness in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding was also determined in this study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Emotional intelligence (EI) is crucial for the educational and social development of individuals with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding, enhancing adaptive behavior, academic success, and social integration. (Sivasubramanian, 2019). By prioritizing emotional development alongside cognitive abilities, educators and policymakers can create inclusive environments that improve outcomes for learners with ID or difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding. (Vovchenko et al., 2022).

2. METHOD

Research Design

The present study analyzes the association between Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Practices Readiness, which are effective in supporting learners with problems remembering things, focusing, targeting the attention as well as the understanding-based concept of this study. A Quantitative Predictive Correlation design is used to obtain the need of studying whether 1 variable can predict another with/without any manipulative or controlling principle (Rashid, 2012). By using quantitative research method, researchers can make predictions on possible future scenarios using numerical data and statistical methods, which provide insights to enable data-driven decision-making and strategic planning (Witteloostuijn, 2022).

Quantitative research involves objective measurement and the statistical connection between the research and the data collected using samples, questionnaires, and surveys (Brians, 2011). It emphasizes numerical patterns and generalizability across groups, as well as precise, convergent reasoning, as opposed to exploratory or divergent thinking (McNabb, 2008). Using this method, the study investigates the extent to which Emotional Intelligence and preparedness for teaching affect the capacity of educators to assist students with cognitive impairments, establishing a basis for empirical learnings. This research design is appropriate because it intends to determine significantly the relationship of investigating the direct and indirect relationships between the following variables:

- Independent Variable (IV): Emotional Intelligence
- Independent Variable (IV): Readiness in Teaching Practices
- Dependent Variable (DV): Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding.

This study will be conducted within the schools division of Davao City implementing inclusive education specifically – special education. As a city of inclusivity, this will be a suitable place to conduct this study. Hence, the division of Davao City comprises 34 districts which are already implementing inclusive education.

There will be 7 selected public elementary schools in one of the districts in the Division of Davao City. These schools are promoting inclusivity for at least 5 years. And these General Education teachers are handling General Education classes or inclusive teachers that are handling intellectual disability for at least 1 year. The respondents of the study will be limited to 200 public elementary school teachers from the 7 schools in the district including the newly hired and permanent teachers who were selected teachers handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding through random sampling technique. The respondents were selected from the sample population.

Research Instrument

The research instruments will be used in this study to determine the relationship between emotional intelligence, readiness in teaching practices and effectiveness in handling difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding. The standardized questionnaires will be given to the respondents and will be submitted to the expert validators for assessment and will be subjected to statistical treatment using the general average computation.

Teachers' Readiness. This is adapted from University of Central Florida's Center for Distributed Learning. It consists of three indicators namely: technical skills, teaching strategies and classroom management with a total of fifteen items.

Third, the questionnaire for Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding This questionnaire is based on established frameworks and studies on teacher effectiveness, emotional intelligence, and inclusive education which was adapted and modified from the study titled "The Development of Social-Emotional Competence in Teachers: A Key Consideration for Addressing Student and Teacher Well-being. Educational Psychology Review Collie, R. J. (2021). Respondents will rate the questionnaire based on the following criteria when evaluating teachers' collaboration education: 5 Always, 4 Oftentimes, 3 Sometimes, 2 Seldom, and 1 Never.

Procedure and Analysis

In this study, defining the role of the researcher is important particularly in the qualitative phase since it is analogous with maintaining the rigor and credibility of the various aspects of the research pursuit. As such, the researcher is the primary individual who writes, encodes and conducts the research. This means that the researcher is the one doing all the necessary work to finish and accomplish this study.

Thus the researcher will secure a letter of permission to conduct the study from the Dean of the Graduate School of Holy Cross of Davao College. The researcher will submit a letter of request to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent

of Davao City, then to the school heads of the selected public elementary schools. The researcher will send an informed consent form to the respondents online to determine their willingness to participate in the study and also they will be oriented on the objectives of the study and its significance.

Lastly, data gathering will be done through online survey questionnaires and Google forms. The researcher will ask the respondents of the study to respond to an online survey and they will be requested to answer the questions honestly so that the validity and reliability of the data will be elicited. The researcher will exert an effort to retrieve the responses to achieve the 100 percent return rate of the questionnaires. The completed questionnaires will be organized accordingly and the results will be collated and tabulated before subjecting it for statistical treatment. The data will be analyzed and interpreted based on the purpose of the study.

In this study, ethical considerations are seen as a crucial step in producing high-quality research output. As it reflects the legitimacy of an ideal research, this approach has a greater impact on the research itself. The Holy Cross of Davao College-Research Ethics Committee (HCDC-REC) will examine the study before it is carried out to make sure it is carried out in an ethical manner. As a result, this study followed the HCDC-REC methodology, which is further detailed as follows:

Social Value. This study addresses to develop a valid and reliable instrument that will measure the emotional intelligence and readiness of teachers handling learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding. The results of this study will be useful in determining if there is or is not a relationship between emotional intelligence and readiness of teachers that will be useful for the betterment of the implementation of special needs education.

Informed Consent. Respect for people is the recognition of participants' rights, including the right to be informed about the study, the right to freely decide whether to participate in a study, and the right to withdraw at any time without penalty (Capron, 2011). After the grant of the request to conduct the study, the researcher communicated with the 8 identified schools that are at least implementing special education and handling learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding.

Then, before data collection begins, they will provide an informed consent form. It was physically administered to the designated research participants in accordance with the stringent health guidelines specified by the IATF, including but not limited to social seclusion, face mask wear, and hand hygiene. The researcher always explained these procedures to the participants. The consent form outlines the study's goals, the interview's procedures, potential risks and discomforts, the study's advantages and significance, the chance for participants to ask questions before and during the research interview, the assurance that no coercion or pressure will be used, and the freedom to withdraw at any time and for any reason if they feel that it should be withdrawn.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The participants will comply with the google form sent. In the google form it is stated that their security is the primary concern. Their information is withheld and known by the researcher alone. All the data including the school they serve are marked black and only known by the researcher. The google form sent will be securely kept with password protection and only the researcher can access. In the case of printed copies, the researcher will store it into a locked and safe cabinet while study is on-going. Prior to the interview, participants signed an informed consent form in which the topics of anonymity, confidentiality, and privacy were also covered. Likewise, after the study was complete, the researcher removed all electronic data and destroyed all paper copies.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. Respondents are free from risks because the data gathering will be done online. Since responses on the interview are through online forms, their responses will be kept and only the researcher can access. After finishing their response, they will be given a certificate of recognition in their meritorious support in this study. Also, even though there is no direct benefit to the respondents from participating in the study. However, the information that the respondents may provide may help the DepEd officials in crafting various activities towards the improvement of special education in the country.

Justice. The ethical requirement to equally distribute the burdens and benefits of the research might be summed up as the justice principle. It is the responsibility of the researcher to make sure that fair methods are followed to choose research participants. Selection criteria were established based on participant sampling to prevent biases. By providing a straightforward token and utilizing general language in the acknowledgement section of the report, participants were thanked for taking part in the study.

Transparency. The researcher made sure that any potential conflicts of interest were reported to the study's participants. The study's results were presented in a soft bound copy to the graduate school for students' use as references, and they were also made available to the participants through a public forum.

Qualification of Researcher. The researcher is currently enrolled in Holy Cross of Davao College, under the graduate school program. Hence, this is a research requirement of the subject Research Methods in Education Quantitative/Qualitative (MAEM – Thesis A). Moreover, the researcher is a licensed public school teacher and has been teaching learners with disabilities for more than 10 years in the division of Davao City. When it comes to the conduct of this study, the researcher is aware of the proper protocols and has been conducting school research. Also, with the help of the adviser, the researcher will be guided in the inquiry of this study. The researcher sought the statistician's assistance and continued to refer to her at each stage, especially when it came to the presentation and analysis of the findings. Eventually, the final edition of this research incorporated the opinions and suggestions of the expert panel.

Adequacy of Facilities. The study's necessary facilities were convenient and easily accessible, according to the researcher. To broaden and strengthen the analysis and interpretation of the obtained data, library and online resources were made available for extra readings and references. There were also additional resources that were really helpful. The researcher's mentor was also instructed to be reachable at all times for consultations. Finally, the group of specialists was asked for insightful comments and recommendations. They were also requested and consulted to assist the researcher both in carrying out the study and in disseminating the findings.

Community Involvement. Before beginning this investigation, written approval from the HCDC-REC and the dean of the graduate school were requested. Prior to conducting the study, the researcher also obtained approval from the various school principals as well as the Superintendent of the Schools Division of the Division of Davao City. Participants' informed consent is obtained by a google form, and they receive orientation to ensure that they understood everything about taking part in the study. Also, the researcher's end result was focused on creating a survey tool that the academic community could use. Finally, the researcher reaffirmed that no prejudice or discrimination would be used at any point during this study, especially in relation to an individual's age, gender, political and religious beliefs, civil status, race, ethnicity, culture, and local traditions.

In gathering the data for this study, the following steps were done:

First, the authority was consulted for permission to perform the study by the researcher. The institution's Graduate School Dean was consulted for approval prior to securing an endorsement. The same approval was then obtained from the Davao City Schools Division Superintendent and the corresponding school heads, along with the institution's Graduate School Dean's support.

The responders will receive an online informed consent form from the researcher to gauge their interest in taking part in the study, and they will also be informed of the goals and importance of the study. Finally, Google forms and online survey questionnaires will be used to collect data. To determine the validity and reliability of the data, the researcher will ask the study's participants to complete an online survey. They will be asked to answer all questions truthfully. To ensure that every questionnaire is returned, the researcher will make every attempt to find the answers. Before subjecting the results to statistical analysis, the completed questionnaires will be arranged appropriately, and the results will be collected and tallied. The analysis and interpretation of the data will be done in light of the study's objectives.

Data will be tallied using SPSS and will be analyzed descriptively using the following statistical tools.

Descriptive Statistics. This study will utilize the mean as it will be used to interpret the data. Standard Deviation (SD) to measure its variability. The Pearson-r will be used to test the relationship between the teachers emotional intelligence and effectiveness in handling learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding. To be significant, the probability value must be less than the alpha level at 0.05.

The researcher made use of the following statistical tools in analyzing the results of the study:

Mean. To address the study's objectives, the mean was used to determine the average levels between Emotional Intelligence, Readiness in Teaching Practices: Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding.

Standard Deviation (SD) was used as a statistical tool to measure the variability or dispersion of responses regarding Emotional Intelligence and Readiness in Teaching Practices Effectiveness in handling learners with difficulties in remembering, concentrating, paying attention, and understanding.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. This tool was utilized to measure the strength and significance of the relationships between Emotional Intelligence, Readiness in Teaching Practices: Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding.

Multiple Regression Analysis. It will be used to determine the significant relationship between the emotional intelligence, readiness of teachers and effectiveness in handling learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding.

The research strictly adhered to ethical protocols established by the University of Mindanao Ethics Committee, obtaining necessary approvals from school administrators and ensuring participants were suitable and adequately informed about risks and data handling. The study was conducted under protocol number UMERC-2024-169, with an accompanying UMERC approval certificate, ensuring that participant's rights and confidentiality were upheld throughout the research process.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study are reviewed in terms of the influence of teachers' emotional intelligence and readiness upon their teaching strategies and classroom management in the presence of students with memory, concentration and attention difficulties, as well as poor understanding. Using the data, they want to find out if there is any significant relationship between the teachers' emotional intelligence and how they meet the challenges above, and to what extent emotional intelligence plays a part in their overall teaching aptitude.

This paper investigates through statistical analysis the impact of emotional intelligence and teaching readiness on classroom instruction, student engagement and overall ability to facilitate student learning for those with cognitive difficulties. The findings are a glimpse into whether emotional intelligence is a crucial key factor or practical teaching preparedness is essential in tackling these challenges accordingly. This research aims to help educators and policymakers recognize elements that improve teaching performance and student learning outcomes.

As shown in Table 1, Descriptive Table the Emotional Intelligence variable obtained the standard deviation result of 0.14 and 4.26 mean value of a "High Level," indicates that the teacher's emotional intelligence dimension is always manifested. For Readiness in Teaching Practices indicators, yielded a standard deviation of 0.26 and a mean score of 4.30 or a "very high level," implying that the teacher's Teachers' readiness is always evident. Readiness in Teaching Practices is divided into two sub variables Classroom Instruction and Curriculum Content. Classroom Instruction got standard deviation of 0.27 and a mean of 4.30 and Curriculum Content got Standard Deviation of 0.30 and a mean of 4.30. both got "very high level." For Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding got the standard deviation of 0.23 and has the highest mean score of 4.31, or a "very high level," implying that the teacher's effectiveness is always observed. Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding have five sections one is Instructional Strategies with Standard Deviation of 0.32 and mean 4.30. Two is Classroom Management and Student Engagement with standard deviation of 0.32 and mean of 4.31. Four is Emotional and Social Support with standard deviation of 0.30 and mean of 4.33. Fifth is Professional Development and Readiness with standard deviation of 0.32 and mean of 4.30. These five sections valued "very high level" implying that the teacher's effectiveness is always observed.

Table 1: Descriptive Table

Variables and Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Emotional Intelligence	0.14	4.26	Very High
Readiness in Teaching Practices	0.26	4.30	Very High
Classroom Instruction	0.27	4.30	Very High
Curriculum Content	0.30	4.29	Very High
Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention, and Understanding	0.23	4.31	Very High
Instructional Strategies	0.32	4.30	Very High
Classroom Management and Student Engagement	0.32	4.31	Very High
Assessment and Feedback	0.31	4.30	Very High
Emotional and Social Support	0.30	4.33	Very High
Professional Development and Readiness	0.32	4.30	Very High

The findings revealed that Emotional Intelligence, Readiness in Teaching in Teaching Practices, Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding got an overall descriptive level of Very High. Implying that it always manifested, always evident and always observed.

Table 2: Correlation Table

Effectiveness Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention, and Understanding				
Independent Variables	r	p-value	Decision on H₀	Interpretation
Emotional Intelligence	.217	.002	Reject	Significant
Readiness in Teaching Strategies	.342	.000	Reject	Significant

In Table 2, Emotional Intelligence is correlated with Effectiveness Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding with an r-value of .217 and a p-value of .002. This shows a significant strong positive correlation between the variables, indicating that teacher's emotional Intelligence shows Effectiveness in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding. Similarly, Readiness in Teaching Practices and Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding demonstrated a strong positive correlation with a value of .342 and a p-value of .000, indicating that teacher's readiness in teaching practices correlated with Effectiveness Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention and Understanding. This shows a significant strong positive correlation between the variables, These correlation results lead to the rejection of the first (H_{01}) null hypothesis.

The correlation coefficient (R) of 0.363 indicates a low to moderate Influence between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Meanwhile, the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.132$) suggests that 13.2% of the variation in the effectiveness of handling learners with cognitive difficulties is explained by Emotional Intelligence and Readiness in Teaching Practices. The F-value of 14.985 with a p-value of 0.000 signifies that the overall model is statistically significant, meaning the combined effect of the independent variables contributes meaningfully to the dependent variable.

Analyzing the influence of individual independent variables, Emotional Intelligence has an unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.217$), indicating a positive relationship with the dependent variable. However, its p-value of 0.064 is greater than the 0.05 significance level, suggesting that its effect is not statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis (H_0) is not rejected, implying that Emotional Intelligence does not significantly impact teachers' effectiveness in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding.

On the other hand, Readiness in Teaching Strategies has an unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.271$), also showing a positive influence on the dependent variable. Unlike Emotional Intelligence, its p-value of 0.000 is well below 0.05, indicating statistical significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that Readiness in Teaching Strategies significantly enhances teachers' effectiveness in handling learners with difficulty in remembering, concentrating, paying attention and understanding. These findings highlight that while Emotional Intelligence may be beneficial, it is the practical readiness in teaching strategies that plays a more crucial role in addressing the learning needs of these learners.

Table 3: Degree of Influence Table

Effectiveness in Handling Learners with Difficulty in Remembering, Concentrating, Paying Attention, and Understanding							
Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Decision on H₀	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.		
(Constant)	2.218	.491		4.514	.000		
Emotional Intelligence	.217	.117	.129	1.862	.064	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Readiness in Teaching Strategies	.271	.062	.304	4.388	.000	Reject	Significant

$R = .363$; $R^2 = .132$; $F\text{-value} = 14.985$; $p\text{-value} = 0.000$

Table 2 presents the correlation between teachers' emotional intelligence, readiness in teaching strategies, and their effectiveness in managing learners with difficulties in remembering, concentrating, paying attention, and understanding. The results reveal that emotional intelligence has a weak yet significant positive correlation ($r = .217$, $p = .002$) with teaching effectiveness, indicating that while higher emotional intelligence enhances classroom management, its overall impact is limited. Conversely, readiness in teaching strategies exhibits a stronger significant positive correlation ($r = .342$, $p = .000$) with teaching effectiveness, suggesting that teachers who are well-equipped with instructional strategies and professional development are more effective in assisting learners with cognitive challenges. Since both correlations are statistically significant, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected, confirming that both emotional intelligence and teaching readiness have a positive relationship with teaching effectiveness.

Table 3 explores the extent to which emotional intelligence and readiness in teaching strategies influence teaching effectiveness. The findings indicate that while emotional intelligence has a positive influence ($B = 0.217$), it is not statistically significant ($p = .064$), suggesting that emotional intelligence alone does not substantially impact teachers' effectiveness in managing learners with cognitive difficulties. In contrast, readiness in teaching strategies has a stronger influence ($B = 0.271$) and is statistically significant ($p = .000$), highlighting that teachers' preparedness encompassing instructional strategies, classroom management, and curriculum planning plays a more vital role in teaching effectiveness. Additionally, the overall model ($R^2 = .132$) shows that only 13.2% of the variation in teaching effectiveness is explained by these two factors, indicating that other unexamined variables likely contribute significantly to teaching effectiveness.

Although emotional intelligence is positively linked to teaching effectiveness, it does not have a significant impact in regression analysis. This could be because practical teaching skills, such as classroom management and teaching strategies, play a more substantial role in driving learning outcomes. Furthermore, teaching effectiveness is shaped by various factors not considered in the study, including experience, subject knowledge, institutional support, and student engagement techniques. The sample may also consist of teachers with already high emotional intelligence, limiting the variation in its effect.

In conclusion, while emotional intelligence contributes to building strong relationships with students, the study suggests that focusing on professional development in teaching strategies is more essential for enhancing teaching effectiveness, particularly when working with learners who face cognitive challenges.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The findings of the study reveal that teachers have a strong professional foundation for inclusive education because of their exceptionally high emotional intelligence scores, preparedness for teaching, and ability to work well with students who have special needs. This has a favorable impact on the current systems for supporting and developing teachers. Furthermore, the substantial positive correlation between teaching effectiveness, teaching preparation, and emotional intelligence suggests that these components are interrelated and work together to create a welcoming and inclusive learning environment. The study also revealed that the only factor that significantly predicts teacher success is preparedness in teaching techniques, highlighting the critical role that practical instructional competences have in helping teachers manage students who struggle with memory, focus, attention, and comprehension. This emphasizes that creating successful teaching methods should take precedence over concentrating only on emotional characteristics or perceived preparedness.

Based on study's findings, teachers are highly effective at helping students who struggle with memory, focus, attention, and comprehension. They also demonstrate a high degree of emotional intelligence and preparation in their teaching methods. Strong positive correlations between these variables imply that they are intimately connected and work together to create a welcoming and inclusive learning environment. The significance of practical instructional abilities in handling students with special needs is highlighted by the fact that the only factor that emerged as a significant predictor of teacher performance was preparation in teaching practices. Although general preparedness and emotional intelligence are useful qualities, the findings highlight that the most important factor in meeting the particular difficulties faced by these students is the capacity to implement efficient teaching techniques.

Recommendation

1. Regular in-service training programs that emphasize inclusive and adaptive teaching approaches should be given top priority by the Department of Education and school administrators at the basic education level. These should include multisensory teaching methods, differentiated instruction strategies, and behavior management tactics designed especially to support students who have trouble focusing, remembering, paying attention, and comprehending. Since teaching methods have a big impact on how effective teachers are, these programs will give teachers the useful skills they need to deal with these issues more skillfully.

2. Comprehensive, classroom-based preparedness modules should be incorporated into the curricula of teacher education programs. These ought to consist of case-based learning, practical experiences, and targeted training on how to work with students who have particular learning needs. Prioritizing the practical implementation of instructional strategies can guarantee that future educators are highly prepared, which will immediately enhance their efficacy in inclusive classrooms.

3. Despite not being a significant predictor in this study, teachers' high levels of emotional intelligence are a great advantage. Through organized programs like peer mentorship programs, workshops on mental wellness, and frequent teacher reflection sessions, schools should uphold and encourage this. Indirectly supporting the maintenance of efficient and compassionate teaching methods, these programs can aid in preventing emotional exhaustion and fostering long-term teacher resilience.

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